

IMPACT OF EXCESSIVE USE OF VIDEO GAMES ON ACADEMIC MOTIVATION; MEDIATING ROLE OF SLEEP QUALITY AMONG UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

In an era where video games have captured the hearts of people of all ages, a striking phenomenon is emerging – a surge in gaming among university students. However, this gaming trend may be casting a dark shadow on their academic pursuits. This study delves deep into the lives of these students, investigating the consequences of their gaming habits. Objectives of this study were to determine the relationship between excessive use of video games, academic motivation and determine the mediating role of sleep quality. Sample included university students (N=400, m=139, f=261) distinguishing them into excessive and non-excessive gamers, The sample was taken from IIUI and UOW universities. The comprehensive Sleep Quality Scale comprised of 25 items, to assess their sleep quality. To investigate the gaming time, Gaming addiction scale (short version) containing 7 items was applied and academic motivation scale containing 28 items was used to measure academic motivation. These scales were used to determine whether excessive gaming affected academic motivation and whether sleep quality played a mediating role between game time and academic motivation. Findings indicated that there was not a significant relationship of excessive use of video games with academic motivation and sleep quality did not mediate the relation between these two variables. This implies that excessive use of video games by students will not reduce sleep quality as well as academic motivation.

Keywords. Gaming time, Academic motivation, Sleep quality.

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the study

In 1998, internet addiction was first identified by Young as a distinct clinical illness (Young, 1998). Recently, DSMV expanded its definition of addiction to include internet gaming disorder (IGD). Across the globe, playing video games has surpassed all other forms of entertainment for kids (Anderson et al, 2001). Almost all Iranian teenagers (93%) play video games, with nearly identical rates among boys (93%) and girls (96%), according to a study done in Iran (Allahverdi-pour et al, 2010). Seventy-five percent of teenagers in the West spend at least one hour per week playing video games (Islam et al., 2020), and the video game business is

massive worldwide, supporting devices such as smart phones, personal computers, and game consoles.

Positive impacts on players' memory, perception, attention, and decision-making are observed when playing these games (Eichenbaum, 2014), yet compulsive gaming is referred to as video game addiction (Lemmens et al., 2009). Issues with falling asleep and staying asleep, as well as the overall quality of sleep, can occur as a result of a gamer's addiction (Lam, 2014c).

Hyperactivity, decreased daytime sleep, and later morning wake times are only some of the issues that might arise from a child's exposure to video games (Ahmed et al., 2022).

The popularity of online games in Pakistan has increased the country's youth's time spent playing video games, which can lead to addiction. Among the many issues they've caused among today's youth is a rise in cases of insomnia, shorter sleep durations, and poorer quality sleep; they also prevent college students from getting the necessary amount of rest each night to function well the following day in class (Rana et al., 2020). One of the most common issues among young people that has a negative impact on their academic performance is insomnia (young, 2009).

Some college students play these games not just in class but also during free time at university cafes, despite the fact that getting a full night's sleep is essential for feeling rested and ready to take on the next day. Some students can't help staying up late playing video games, even when it's keeping them from getting enough rest (king, 2010). Some kids tell their parents they're doing homework when they're really playing video games; others tell their partners they need to spend less time working so they have more time to play video games (young, 2009).

Those who spend more than four hours a day, or thirty hours a week, gaming are considered to be excessive gamers, whereas those who spend less than four hours a day, or thirty hours a week, gaming are considered to be non-excessive gamers (Afzal et al., 2010). Both compulsive gambling and excessive gaming have been categorized as addictive behaviors (TajeroSalguero et al., 200). Video games are played to relax, to get away from daily stresses, and to experience competence and autonomy (Griffiths, 2003; Ryan et al., 2003), while gambling is played for entertainment, stimulates the player, and elicits both positive and negative emotions. Excessive computer and video game play is rewarded because it helps players deal with stress, although this strategy is ineffective (Grusser et al., 2005). Students will be more motivated to study and use English because it is the language of most video games.

Definition of Gaming:

According to Cambridge Dictionary gaming is defined as "an act of playing video games on computers and other electronic devices"

Gaming can be done on PC's consoles such as Play station , Xbox , Nintendo switch and mobile phones.

Excessive use of Video games:

Playing video games for 4 hours a day or more but not having symptoms of addiction is considered excessive gaming (Adžić et al., 2021) which can lead to gaming addiction and internet gaming disorder.

Video Games (battle royal games):

Video games are a type of MMORPG. Games like PUBG, VALORANT, Apex Legends, Call of Duty: Warzone, and Gerena free fire let players create custom avatars to express their personalities and preferences. Students have a hard time putting down these games once they start, and the firms generate millions of dollars off of loot boxes, or digital items, in the games. Regular improvements to these games keep players coming back for more of the same great benefits. Within the first three days of its debut, PUBG made \$7 million (dagdee et al., 2019).

Academic motivation:

- Academic motivation, as defined by Hullman (Hulleman, et al., 2016), is "the desire or interest in engaging with learning and the school experience." Babies' intellectual incentive is evident even in their early days, when they must learn to walk in order to reach a toy or food.

- It is a state of mental and emotional excitement that might boost a student's performance in class (Vallerand et al., 1992).

- A student's motivation to learn is the driving force behind their efforts to study and master course material. A 2014 study by Hakan and Münire

- According to the literature (McClelland, et al., 1953; Omiles et al., 2019; Olowo et al., 2020; Serhan, 2019), academic motivation can be defined as a student's desire (as reflected in approach, persistence, and level of interest) regarding academic subjects when the student's competence is judged against a standard of performance or excellence.

The ability to learn and succeed in school depends on a student's level of academic motivation, which is defined as the "force that causes a student to work toward learning and achieving good grades." Without academic motivation, students are less likely to pay attention in class and more likely to engage in distractions like talking with friends. Only if a student is truly invested in his education will he be able to give his whole attention to his studies both in and out of the classroom. Learning is impossible without the internal drive to study.

- Low physical activity levels.
- Reduced sensory awareness.

Sleep quality

- It is a measurement of how well a person is sleeping
- Its is a personal satisfaction with all aspects of the sleep experience

Individual can't function well without enough sleep. The hypothesis of brain plasticity states that as we sleep, our memories might be solidified. The more time a student spends playing video games at night, the less time he has to sleep, which has been linked to a decline in sleep quality. Since sleep helps us remember everything we learned the day before, it's no surprise that a student's academic performance and motivation hinge on his or her ability to recollect all of the material they've studied (Da Fonseca et al., 2020). People with insomnia are more likely to pay attention to sleep-related stimuli than people with good sleep hygiene (Harris et al 2015), and those people with insomnia are more likely to continue monitoring signals that are related to sleep difficulties (Marchetti et al,2006). The inability to get to sleep is a direct result of the physiological and emotional stimulation that worry about sleep causes (Takano, et al., 2016).Ojio et al. (2016) found that the more time spent playing video games in front of a screen, the more disturbed, slower, and less sleep one gets.

THEORIES OF SLEEP QUALITY

Brain plasticity theory

Infants require up to 14 hours of sleep every day because, according to the brain plasticity theory of sleep, this is when long-term memories are solidified. The brain needs rest in order to make the modifications required to permanently store newly acquired information. Tononi and cerelli proposed this idea. There are anatomical and functional alterations in the brain:

Functional aspect. After a brain has been damaged in a certain area it re-learns skills in another area this is the functional aspect of brain plasticity.

Structural aspect. When brain forms new pathways because of learning this is structural aspect of brain plasticity.

Clean up theory of Sleep

According to this view, the brain's garbage can is emptied during sleep. During sleep, the brain's waste products and poisons are flushed out by an increase in the flow of fluid away from the brain.

Evolutionary theory of Sleep

According to this theory of sleep, sleep is evolved as a mechanism to conserve energy at a time when staying awake is hazardous (Klietman. 1964).

THEORIES OF MOTIVATION

Incentive theory of motivation (ITM)

This theory states that people are motivated by a drive for incentives or reinforcements in other words people will strive to get some kind of reward for their activity and and will act to avoid some kind of punishment. In terms of Academic motivation students will study to get better paying jobs later on or to get good grades and they will try to avoid punishment by teachers for performing poorly.

Self-determination theory (SDT)

This theory was developed by Deci and Ryan, there are 3 types of motivation

1. Intrinsic motivation

People are said to be intrinsically motivated when they are driven to do action by factors other than the potential for monetary gain. A student who is highly motivated by his or her own curiosity, learning, and enthusiasm in the subject at hand is more likely to achieve academic achievement than his or her less-intrinsically-motivated counterparts. When it comes to things like employment, school, and health care, a person's level of intrinsic motivation is a strong predictor of how long he'll stick with it. (Cerasoli et al., 2014) To cite: (Grant & Berry, 2011)

2. Extrinsic motivation

Extrinsic motivation refers to the process of acting in order to obtain some external benefit or to prevent some undesirable outcome. There is a negative correlation between a student's motivation to learn and his or her academic performance. Students whose only motivation for school is the hope of landing a better career or improving their financial situation tend to underachieve academically. If a student, for instance, solely studies to do well on midterms, finals, assignments, quizzes, and so on, he or she is unlikely to continue doing so until they have achieved their desired grade(s).

3. A-motivation:

A-motivated behaviors are ones that lack any sort of internal or external stimulus to prompt them. When a student lacks intrinsic or extrinsic desire to study or participate in class, they are said to be

"amotivated," and they eventually stop doing either gaming or studying. It is possible to draw parallels between amotivation and learned helplessness (Abramson, Seligman, & Teasdale, 1978) due to the fact that an unmotivated student will not take pleasure in their studies and will not expect to benefit in any way from their efforts. The word "amotivation" was coined by psychologists Markland and Tobin (2004) to describe a state in which people lack the "volitional drive to engage in any activity" (Deci and Ryan, 1985). When people lack motivation, it can have a severe impact on their mental and emotional health.

According to the work of Deci and Ryan, there are three distinct requirements for a person to feel driven and make progress in their personal development.

Independence 2)Expertise Thirdly, a sense of connection.

- When we're able to rely on our own internal drives, we satisfy the demand for autonomy.
- Competence leads to the development of new abilities, and when we believe we have the capabilities to complete a task, we are more inclined to do so.
- To feel connected to other individuals is to experience relatedness.

Association of Video games and addiction:

Addiction is described as "a state of psychological or physical dependence on the use of alcohol or drugs," according to the American Psychological Association's (APA) definition of psychology. Substance dependence and other types of behavioral illnesses, such as compulsive gambling, compulsive internet use, and sexual addiction, are all synonymous with this word.

Addiction can also be defined as "the compulsive need to repeat a rewarding behavior despite the risk of negative consequences in the long run" (for instance, drug usage or excessive gaming).

We will call someone an addict of video games when he/she will start to exhibit symptoms of addiction : when video games start negatively affecting social life, sleep , work/school, and withdrawal symptoms when leaving playing of video games

Theories of Addiction:

Classical theory of addiction:

According to the traditional view of addiction, withdrawal symptoms manifest after a person stops

using drugs, and this is what drives them to start using again. As reported by Patton (A.) in 2006

Behavioral theory of addiction:

These theories propose that behavior is maintained through reinforcement, or the results of previous activity. Animals exposed to an overabundance of medications have been shown to self-medicate with larger doses than they would otherwise. Both the direct effects of the drug and the drug's effects on reinforcers (such as social or sexual reinforcers) or behavioral effects (such as greater attention) contribute to the reinforcing nature of drugs with effects analogous to those of video games (Altman et al, 1996).

Psychoanalytic theory of addiction:

According to psychoanalytic theory, people who were physically or sexually abused as children have a diminished capacity to deal with emotions and stress, which leads them to begin using drugs, which in turn leads to addiction. The same is true for people who begin playing video games as a means of coping with stress.

Role of neurotransmitter dopamine:

The neurotransmitter dopamine is responsible for our experience of pleasure and reward. The significance it plays in the brain's control of rewards and motor activity is unparalleled. The ventral tegmental area of the brain is responsible for the production of dopamine, which is then transported to the nucleus accumbens and the prefrontal cortex.(Oligun et al., 2016).Excess dopamine levels in the brains of schizophrenics are the cause of their symptoms.

Dopamine theory of addiction:

According to Melis, "In brief, the hypothesis contends that decreased dopamine function in addicted subjects results in decreased interest to non-drug-related stimuli and increased sensitivity to the drug of choice," suggesting that restoring dopamine function might be therapeutically advantageous for those struggling with addiction. According to Melis, once a person is addicted to a substance or a certain stimuli, only that drug or stimulus can produce the same amounts of dopamine, as the body is unable to produce it in natural ways once the stimulus is removed.If a person is addicted to video games, they may experience withdrawal symptoms when they

stop playing and will desperately want to pick up where they left off.

Addiction of video games :

People have been reporting addiction-like symptoms, such as playing video games for long periods of time to the exclusion of other activities like socializing, going to school, and paying bills, and even as early as the 1980s, it was recognized that the potential for people to abuse video games just like drugs exists, and it was suggested that counselors should remain vigilant. Video game addiction has been compared to that of gambling; it has also been linked to problems with motivation and self-control; and it falls under the umbrella term "internal gaming disorder" (IGD) (Kuss, 2013). Video game addiction is defined by DSM-5 as "persistent and repetitive use of the internet to play games frequently with other gamers, resulting in significant distress and psychological changes" (Saqib et al., 2017). Excessive gaming leads to addiction because it triggers the brain to produce dopamine, which then causes withdrawal when the player cuts back or quits playing. The player's quality of sleep will suffer as a result of the time spent playing video games. Because dopamine levels decline with time, an addicted gamer will desire to play more and more despite the negative effects. Neurological changes occur when a person begins playing video games and is repeatedly exposed to them over time (Meng et al., 2015), and these changes eventually lead to a long-term addiction (Gentile et al., 2009). Video game addicts are similar to alcoholics and drug addicts in that they can't function in everyday life until they're immersed in a virtual world (Yen et al., 2019).

Video games in males vs females :

Research found out that males spent more time playing video games as compared to females were more skilled at them, Dindar (2018b) another research investigated and found that stereotype that males are better at video games and spend more time playing video games as compared to females is only slightly true and that gaming culture is more hostile towards females, Dindar (2018c) yet another research conducted in Germany found that males played more video games as compared to their female counterparts, (Rehbein et al 2016)

1.2) Problem Statement:

According to literature support excessive use of video games effects sleep quality ,and thus I hypothesized that problematic use of video games

will effect academic motivation with sleep quality will have mediator role.

1.3) Significance of the Study:

Researchers were able to determine whether or not gaming negatively affects kids' sleep quality and whether or not persistent gamers are less motivated to succeed in school. Parents will be able to decide if they want to take away their children's cell phones and computers, and students will have a better idea of whether or not gaming is a healthy part of their life. It will aid students in figuring out whether or not gaming is harming their rest. It was useful in determining whether or not gaming had an adverse effect on our desire to learn.

1.4) Objectives of the Study:

- To assess the mediating role of sleep quality and academic motivation between role of excessive use of video games and academic motivation among excessive gamers and non-excessive gamers of university students.
- To explore the association among sleep quality ,academic motivation, excessive use of video games in academic motivation excessive gamers and normal gamers
- To examine the difference based on socio-demographic variables in terms of academic motivation ,excessive use of video games and sleep quality

1.5) Hypotheses:

H1= The excessive use of video games will be negatively associated with sleep quality, academic motivation

H2= Sleep quality will play mediating role between academic motivation and excessive use of video games.

H3=There is a significant difference on bases of demographic variables on sleep quality academic motivation and excessive use of video games among university students.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Review of related literature:

The more he plays video games before night, the less restful his sleep will be, the later he'll go to bed, and the more exhausted he'll feel during the day (Adam et al. 2007, King et al., 2013, Van den Bulck, 2004). Most people who have trouble sleeping report feeling irritable and less productive the following day (Espie and Lindsay, 1987). Numerous studies have

found that total sleep deprivation has a lesser influence on performance the following day. Studies on the effects of sleep deprivation on cognition and motivation have shown that those with psychopathology are more likely to experience poor motivation and cognitive dysfunction the day after less sleep than those without psychopathology; in other words, healthy individuals do not experience diminished motivation as a result of sleep deprivation, but those with psychopathology do. Sleep deprivation can have varying effects on performance, depending on the nature of the task at hand (Wilkinson, 1965). The majority of time spent playing video games occurs at night, making it a nocturnal pastime (Hale and Guan, 2015).

(Exelmans et al., 2014) conducted a research on 844 French people in Flanders about their use of social media and they used PSQI scale to measure sleep quality scale, they conducted face to face interviews of participants, they used Fatigue assessment scale (FAS) Bergen insomnia scale (BIS) and video gaming volume in which they determined how much video games participants played, how many hours a day they played and whether higher use of video games is related to poor sleep quality, they found that long hours of use of video games make them to go to bed time later which causes poor sleep quality (Turel et al., 2017) about link of obesity and video game usage and sweet drinks, they found out that video game usage is linked to higher consumption of sweet drinks during play time, and more hours spent playing video games closer to sleep time causes poor sleep quality, they used PSQI to determine sleep quality, they also found out that video games cause higher obesity and abdominal adiposity. (Rana et al., 2020) Hostel residents in Pakistan's twin cities of Islamabad and Rawalpindi reported experiencing financial difficulties, poor sleep, playing mobile games before bed, sleeping on uncomfortable mattresses, and being subjected to noisy living conditions, but the study did not draw any firm conclusions about the impact of these issues on students' academic performance.

Long-term gaming was found to result in clinically significant sleep loss and cognitive abnormalities associated with chronic reduced sleep time, according to a study that looked at the impact of gaming on sleep quality. According to Young, those who are addicted to video games often lose track of time, putting their gaming ahead of sleep, friends, and family. Successful students' strategy is to play hard and study hard (Adi et al., 2021). Heavy gamers

have lower academic performance than non-heavy gamers. The ideal amount of time to game is between three and four hours. Contrary to popular misconception, gaming does not have a negative impact on pupils' academic achievement. Science, math, and reading scores do not suffer as a result of pupils' time spent playing video games (Drummond et al., 2014).

Axelsson et al. (2010) found that a lack of sleep makes people drowsier throughout the day, which in turn decreases their motivation to take part in a variety of activities. Sleep deprivation is also a symptom of many sleep-related disorders. Borbely (1982) argues that circadian and homeostatic processes regulate sleep in the same way they manage the satisfaction of other basic needs like thirst, hunger, and so on. Longer sleep duration was associated with fewer problem behaviors, and sleep served as a mediator between screen time (including gaming) and problem behavior (Guerrero et al., 2019).

Insomnia was found to be more common among video game players compared to non-players, and the prevalence of depression and anxiety among addicted gamers was found to be higher than that of non-addicted gamers. However, the health problems of addicted gamers improved after they got married. As of 2020 (Sosso et al.). Students who were addicted to video games slept less and experienced more psychological distress than their non-addicted peers, and this was more common in females than in males, according to a study of Saudi Arabian adolescents conducted in schools (Saquib et al., 2017b). Goldfield et al. (2015) found that spending more time in front of a screen negatively affected individuals' psychological and social well-being. Academic pressure has been linked to compulsive gaming, according to a study (Jeon et al., 2022).

Since most people have to get up early for work or school, they play video games late at night instead of sleeping, which has detrimental cognitive consequences (Wolf et al., 2014). Cain and Gradisar (2010) found that several studies found that having electronics in the bedroom was associated with less quality sleep. In a study conducted by Van den Bulck (2004), kids who spent more time playing video games reported feeling more exhausted than their non-gaming peers. Internet video game addiction (IVGA) has been defined as the inability to limit internet use with psychosocial dysfunction (Wiley et al., 2017), and has recently gained more attention in the psychiatric and psychological communities due

to its negative effects on sleep. Study conducted by (Altintas et al., 2019) found intensity of video games directly predicted poor sleep quality another study

by (Parachia et al., 2018) found exposure to video games caused altered sleep patterns and which lead to insufficient and low quality sleep.

Depressive symptoms and insomnia, as defined by the insomnia severity index, have been linked to playing massively multiplayer online role-playing games, according to a number of studies. Playing massively multiplayer online games to an unhealthy degree decreases the quality and length of sleep (Lawrence T.L, 2014). Adverse symptoms in critical areas of life, such as mood and sleep, were observed by those with high addiction rates to MMORPGs; this calls for a preventative program to curb excessive play of these games (Achab et al, 2011). According to a survey of young Germans, Counter-Strike has the highest market share (27%) among popular video games. 16 percent of gamers enjoy FIFA Soccer, 14 percent GTA, and 10 percent Grand Theft Auto. Online role-playing games (9.8%) World of Warcraft (7.8%) Conflict (5.9%) Warcraft(4.9%)World of Warcraft, an MMORPG, is more popular among German youth than Pro Evolution Soccer (4.8%) or Guild Wars (2.7%), and studies have shown that players of this game are more likely to be addicted to video games or to develop such an addiction in the future (Rehbein et al., 2010b). According to a study conducted among residents of Taiwan, video gamers are more likely to suffer from sleeplessness. Among American adolescents aged 8 to 18 years old, just 8% reported a problematic pattern of video game use (Gentile, 2009). Late night gaming reduces the amount of sleep a person gets, which in turn impacts their focus the following day (Wolf et al., 2014). This effect can be seen even after just one night of gaming.

Hoef et al. (2008) found that fMRI scans of men revealed significantly higher levels of activation and functional connectivity in the meso-cortico-limbic system, suggesting that men are more likely to be drawn to and "hooked" on video games. To wit: after repeated performance of a video game, dopamine is released in quantities similar to pharmacological challenge, which is the same as reduced production In dopamine after repeated use of psychostimulants (Winstien A, 2010), so video game addiction is similar to substance addiction and similar to behavioral addictions like gambling, overeating, sex, and shopping. Effects on reward and sensitization keep players coming back for more (Thelman et al., 2007).

Video games have been popular for a variety of reasons, but some research suggests they may not be an effective stress reliever at all (Han et al., 2009). Research has shown that the impacts of video game addiction are minimal, affecting only a small subset of the population, and diminishing rapidly as play is curtailed (Griffith, 2008). According to Griffiths, the key distinction between excessively healthy pursuits and destructive addictions is that in the former, value is added to one's life, while in the latter, it is subtracted (Griffiths, 2007). Similarly to how money is used to maintain addicted behavior in slot machines, Griffiths has stated that video game addiction can be understood as a non-financial kind of gambling (Griffiths, 1995).

A student's level of intrinsic motivation significantly affects his or her ability to study. According to

research (Vallerand, R. J., & Blssonnette, R. (1992.)), three types of motivation—intrinsic, extrinsic, and amotivation—can be used to predict student performance in the classroom. Students who get enough sleep are more likely to be mastery oriented (i.e., extrinsically motivated), while those who don't fall far short of their potential because of lack of sleep are more likely to be intrinsically motivated. (Edens, 2006) Is driven by a desire to succeed on its own merits (intrinsic motivation). Exam failure or difficulty is more common among students who report getting 30 minutes less sleep each night than kids who take higher grades. Wolfson and Carskadon (1998). Students' academic objectives can be broken down into two categories: mastery goals (when they study to learn something new) and performance goals (when they study to impress others with how clever or capable they are). (Dweck, 1986). Bandura (1986) and Midgely (2002) cite a large body of data showing that students' levels of intrinsic motivation have a direct impact on their performance in school, suggesting that students' levels of intrinsic motivation are directly related to their academic success.

Playing mature video games was also associated with somatic complaints, behavioral problems, and shorter sleep duration. According to studies conducted on children, video game addiction manifests itself in young children through negative effects on study, sleep, social isolation, and the neglect of important responsibilities for school students. Internet addiction, which includes playing online video games, is becoming a severe mental health problem, according to a study conducted on children and adolescents in South Korea (YDK, 2003).

Addiction to video games can impair self-control, which in turn can interfere with school performance and professional development (World Health Organization, 2018). Like the presence of ADHD can be a risk factor for drug use addiction, the presence of ADHD in children also works as a risk factor for developing internet video game addiction (Yoo et al., 2004). Persistent gaming has also been linked to attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (Chan et al., 2006). Similarly, one study found that playing video games in moderation is better for academic performance than neither playing video games at all nor playing video games excessively (Allahverdi-pour et al., 2010), and another study found the same thing (Willoughby, 2008).

Parents should be educated about the benefits of moderate gaming. Students who are intrinsically motivated are more likely to succeed academically than their extrinsically motivated counterparts (Afzal et al., 2010). Extrinsically motivated students are more likely to work hard until they receive their reward, but they are less likely to continue working hard afterward. Playing video games helps student learning, as evidenced by a 2013 study showing that players of a Newton's mechanics video game outperformed those who had not played the game (Snow et al.). Yoon (2014) found that playing educational video games increased students' enthusiasm to learn and their success in a variety of subject areas, including algebra, reading, problem-solving, strategic planning, cooperation, and self-learning regulation. People with higher academic achievement tend to be more motivated in the classroom, while those with lower academic achievement tend to be less motivated. Taylor et al. (2019), Litalien et al. (2019), Taylor et al. (2014), Burton et al. (2006), Ryan and Deci (2020), Kriegbaum, Becker, and Spinath (2018), Sleep converts short-term memory into long-term memory, so getting enough shut-eye is essential for students to retain what they've learned. This idea is central to the restorative theory of sleep, which was proposed by neurologist Dr. Ian Oswald in 2006. People study for two reasons, according to the incentive theory of academic motivation: (a) they want a higher salary by getting a better job, or (b) they are curious about learning more. However, the quality of their sleep has a negative impact on their memory and other academic issues.

Edens (2006) found that decreased sleep quality was associated with decreased self-efficacy, performance-oriented goals, and increased procrastination, he also found that reduced sleep quality was associated with reduced academic performance which is directly related to academic motivation. Topal (2019) found out that in 8th grade students academic performance was higher who had better sleep quality. This finding suggest that academic motivation is directly linked with sleep quality (Altenado et al., 2019) found video games reduced sleep quality and is directly linked with reduced academic performance, academic motivation is direct predictor of academic performance. Same findings were from (Wolf et al., 2014) that reduced sleep quality is associated with video games and it also reduced performance and attention.

2.2 Conceptual Framework:

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research design:

This research was a quantitative study, it was based on cross sectional study

3.2 Population:

Population was university students from Islamabad and Wah Cantt.

3.3 Sampling:

Sample was be N =400 size 139 male and 261 female university students from IIUI and UOW. Sample was employed through stratified sampling technique. Permission was taken from Head of departments in IIUI and UOW then sample was employed through stratified sampling technique. Strata were generated after dividing the participants into male and female, strata were generated based on their gender. After that participants were selected using random sampling technique. Participants were given briefing about the purpose of the study and were given the informed consent was taken by the participants moreover necessary instructions were given to the participants.

3.4 Operational definitions of Variables:

Academic motivation:

Academic motivation is defined by a student's desire (as reflected in approach, persistence, and level of interest) regarding academic subjects when the student's competence is judged against a standard of performance or excellence (McClelland, et al., 1953; Omiles et al., 2019; Olowo et al., 2020; Serhan, 2019)

Sleep quality:

Sleep quality refers to a collection of sleep measures including total sleep time , sleep onset latency , degree of fragmentation, total wake time, sleep efficiency, and sometimes sleep disruptive events such as spontaneous arousals or apnea(Buysse et al.,1989)

Excessive use of video games:

Playing video games for 4 hours a day or more but not having symptoms of addiction is considered excessive gaming (Adžić et al., 2021) which can lead to gaming addiction and internet gaming disorder.

3.5 Instruments:

1. Sleep Quality Scale (SQS):

Sleep quality scale developed by Yi et al., 2006 , researcher will use sleep quality scale SQS (Yi et al., 2006) it measures on a 4 point likert scale.It has an internal consistency of .92, a test retest reliability of .81. The SQS is strongly correlated with results obtained on the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index. Scores achieved by the insomnia sample were significantly higher than those of controls, indicating good construct validity.

2.Acadamic motivation Scale:

Academic Motivation Scale (AMS) is one of the most used instruments to measure the motivation level of students toward learning. A three-subscale model consists of intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation, and amotivation. Academic motivation scale (AMS-C 28) comprises on 28 items and consists of 7 point likert scale internal consistency (mean alpha value = .81) and temporal stability over a one-month period (mean test-retest correlation = .79) (Vallerand et al., 1992)

3.Gaming addiction Scale (GAS):

Gaming addiction scale (GAS) (Lemmens et al., 2009) comprises on 7 items and is on 5 point likert scale, it has internal consistency ($\alpha = 0.85$), concurrent validity of GAS is ($r = 0.549$ to 0.576).The GAS was developed based on seven criteria: salience, tolerance, mood modification, withdrawal, relapse, conflict, and problems (Lemmens et al., 2009). The seven criteria are DSM-based and theory-driven (Griffiths, 2005; Griffiths and Davies, 2005).

3.6 Procedure:

The study was carried out by the permission of departmental research and ethic committee participants. Verbal consent was taken from participants they were given an explanation of the purpose of the study and asked to fill the questionnaire. The total item of all scales comprises 63, regarding sleep quality, gaming addiction, academic motivation. Completed questionnaire were collected from the participants and they were thanked.

3.7 Data analysis :

Data will be analyzed using SPSS software version 22 and Pearson Correlation, T-test and simple linear regression were used for analysis

3.6 Ethical Considerations:

Participants were informed about the purpose of study then they were asked whether they would like to be part of this study or not. Permission was taken from department before administering all the questionnaires.

RESULTS

This chapter includes represents the quantitative data of this study. The study's results are according to the study's objectives and hypothesis. Initially, psychometric properties were calculated. The data obtained by the participants in the way of analyzing their responses on different scales, then summarize this data and presents in frequency table. The Cronbach's Alpha value on each scale is calculated as evidence for the reliability of the scale. Further inferential statistics were done to test the hypothesis of the study like regression, t-test, and correlation.

Table 1

Frequency and Percentages of Demographics Variables (Experimental Group N = 400)

Variables	Categories	f	%
Gender	Male	139	34.8
	Female	261	65.3
Age	18	18	4.5
	19	64	16.0
	20	89	22.3
	21	102	25.5
	22	77	19.3
	23	37	9.3
	24	8	2.0
	25	4	1.0
	26	1	.3
Class	BS 1 st	4	1.0
	BS 2 nd	170	42.5
	BS 3 rd	3	.8
	BS 4 th	42	10.5
	BS 5 th	1	.3
	BS 6 th	123	30.8
	BS 7 th	12	3.0
	BS 8 th	45	11.3
Game Time	less than 4 hours a day	316	79.0
	More than 4 hours a day	84	21.0

This table shows that 139 males and 261 females participated in the study, percentage of males is 34.8% and females is 65.3. Ages of participants are

from 18-26, most of the participants are aged 21 and their percentage is 25.5%, mean of ages is 20.81 and standard deviation is 1.48. Most of the participants

are students of BS class 2nd semester, their percentage is 42%. 316(79.0%) participants played video games less than 4 hours per day and 84(21.0%)

participants played video games more than 4 hours per day.

Table 2:

This table shows frequency of participant score in Gaming addiction scale (GA_T)

Note: GA_T =total score of GAS(Gaming addiction scale)

This table 2 shows that most of the participants in the study were not addicted to video games as indicated by low scored that they obtained in gaming addiction scale (GAS)

Table 3

Psychometric properties and Alpha Coefficients of Scales (N=400)

Measures	No. of items	α	Range		M	SD	Skew.	Kurt.
			Min	Max				
AMS	28	.93	28	196	106.7	32.5	.40	-.35
AMS_S1	12	.89	12	84	45.4	15.6	.40	-.53
AMS_S2	12	.72	12	84	47.6	16.5	.40	-.61
AMS_S3	4	.90	4	42	13.6	5.7	.66	.84
GAS	7	.83	7	41	14.3	6.2	.77	.32
SQS	25	.73	35	96	62.2	9.8	-.00	.04

Note. k = no of items; α = Cronbach's alpha; M = Mean; SD = Standard deviation.

AMS=Academic motivation scale, AMS_S1=Intrinsic motivation, AMS_S2=Extrinsic motivation, AMS_S3=Amotivation, GAS=Gaming addiction scale, SQS=Sleep quality scale.

Table 3 showed the reliability and descriptive statistics of scales used in the study. The sleep quality scale showed good reliability of .73 and the academic motivation scale showed a reliability of .93 which is considered as excellent reliability. Similarly, the gaming addiction scale also displayed excellent internal consistency of .83. Subscales of academic motivation AMS_S1 (Intrinsic motivation) showed reliability of .89, AMS_S2(Extrinsic motivation) showed reliability of .72, AMS_S3 (Amotivation) showed reliability of .90

Table 4

Bivariate Correlations Analysis between all Study Variables

Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6
1 Game time	1	-	-	-	-	-

2 Sleep quality	-.09	1	-	-	-	-
3 Academic motivation	-.10*	.20**	1	-	-	-
4 AMS_S1	-.10*	.19**	.94**	1	-	-
5 AMS_S2	-.09	.17**	.95**	.84**	1	-
6 AMS_S3	-.02	.100*	.40**	.21**	.26**	1

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Note: AMS_S1=intrinsic motivation , AMS_S2=Extrinsic motivation, AMS_S3=Amotivation.

Table 4 presents a correlation matrix depicting the relationships between Sleep Quality Scale (SQS), Gaming Time (GAT), and Academic Motivation Scale (AMT) and subscales of academic motivation Intrinsic motivation (AMS_S1), extrinsic motivation (AMS_S2) and Amotivation (AMS_S3). Relation of Game time (G-Time) with sleep quality was not statistically significant ($r = 0.09, P > 0.05$). Relation of Game time (G_Time) with Academic motivation was statistically significant ($r = -1.00, P < 0.05$) and game time (G_Time) with intrinsic motivation was also statistically significant ($r = -1.00, P < 0.05$). Game time (G_Time) did not have a significant relation with extrinsic motivation ($r =$

.086, $P > 0.05$) and Amotivation ($r = -0.17, p > 0.05$). This shows that when amount of time spent on video games increases then academic motivation and intrinsic motivation will decrease.

Sleep quality (SQS_T) has positive and statistically significant relation with academic motivation (AMS_T) ($r = .195^{**}, P < 0.01$), intrinsic motivation (AMS_S1) ($r = .192^{**}, P < 0.01$), Extrinsic motivation (AMS_S2) ($r = .169^{**}, P < 0.01$) and Amotivation ($r = .10^*, P < 0.05$). This means that if sleep quality increases academic motivation, intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation and amotivation will also increase.

Table 5

t-test analysis between male & female, on variable of AMS, SQS, and GAS

Variable	Male		Female		<i>t</i> (397)	P	95% CI		Cohen's <i>d</i>
	M	SD	M	SD			LL	UL	
1. Academic motivation	112.56	32.81	103.61	32.02	2.62	.009	2.25	15.64	0.27
2. AMS_S1	48.06	15.74	44.01	15.30	2.49	.013	.857	7.24	0.26
3. AMS_S2	50.57	16.85	46.10	16.06	2.59	.010	1.08	7.86	0.27
4. AMS_S3	13.90	5.54	13.49	5.79	.687	.492	-.766	1.59	0.07
5. Sleep quality	61.10	9.80	62.7	9.83	-1.62	.104	-3.70	.348	0.16
6. Gaming addiction	15.9	7.05	13.48	5.59	3.76	.000	1.157	3.69	0.38

Note. M= Mean; SD= Standard Deviation; CI = confidence interval; LL = lower limit, UL = upper limit ; ; AMS_S1= Academic motivation scale subscale 1 ; AMS_S2= Academic motivation scale subscale 2 ; AMS_S3= Academic motivation scale subscale 3 ;

Table 5 revealed significant differences on academic motivation total with $p_{397} = .009$ and $P < .05$, Findings show that male exhibit higher scores on academic motivation ($M = 112.56, SD = 32.81$) when compared with females ($M = 103.61, SD = 32.02$), value of Cohen's *d* was medium $0.27 (< 0.50)$ which indicated a small effect size. Findings revealed a significant differences on intrinsic motivation (AMS_S1) with $t_{397} = .013$ $P < 0.05$ with males ($M = 48.06, SD = 15.74$) and effect size was medium $0.26 (< 0.50)$. Findings show a significant difference in extrinsic motivation (AMS_S2) with

$t(397) = 2.62$ $P < 0.05$ between males ($M = 50.57, SD = 16.85$) when compared with females ($M = 46.1, SD = 16.06$), effect size was medium $0.27 (< 0.50)$. Findings revealed a non significant difference in Amotivation (AMS_S3) with $t(397) = .492$ $P > 0.05$ between males ($M = 13.9, SD = 5.54$) and females ($M = 5.79, SD = 6.87$) effect size was small $0.07 (< 0.2)$. Findings revealed a non-significant difference in sleep quality (SQS_T) with $t(397) = .104$ $P < 0.05$ between males ($M = 61.10, SD = 9.80$) and females ($M = 62.7, SD = 9.83$), effect size was small $0.17 (< 0.20)$.

Findings revealed significant difference in gaming addiction (GA_T) with $t(397)=.000$ $P<0.05$ with

males ($M=15.9,SD=7.05$) and females ($M=13.48,SD=5.59$), effect size was $0.38(<0.50)$

Table 6

Linear Regression Analysis

Variables	B	95% CI for B			B	P
		LL	UL	SE		
Constant	108.04	104.4	111.6	1.8		.00
Gaming time	-6.5	-14.3	1.4	3.5	-.81	.11
R ²	0.07					
F (1,15)	2.6					

Table 6 showed that the result of a simple linear regression analysis of the variables of the study. It showed that gaming time is negatively predicting academic motivation as indicated by negative sign but it is not statistically significant. The overall model was not significant (1,15)= 2.6., $R^2 = .007$ and explained variance of the model 7%.

Table 7

Mediation Estimates (Game time= X; Sleep quality = M; Academic motivation = Y)

Effect	Label	Estimate	SE	95% CI		T	P
				LL	UL		
Indirect	a × b	-.39	.80	-2.2	1.11	-	-
Direct	C	-6.1	3.9	-13.82	1.70	-1.53	.12
Total	c + a × b	-6.5	4.0	-14.34	1.43	-1.60	.10

Table 7 shows the direct effect of Game time vs academic motivation (path c), indirect effect of game time through sleep quality (path a × b) and total effect of game time on academic motivation (path c + a × b). The findings revealed that game time does not significantly predict academic motivation ($\beta = -6.1, p>.05$). Further, game time through sleep quality does not predict academic motivation ($\beta = -6.5, p>.05$). The indirect effect was also not statistically significant.

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Table 8

Mediation Estimates (Game time= X; Sleep quality = M; Intrinsic motivation = Y)

Effect	Label	Estimate	SE	95% CI		T	P
				LL	UL		
Indirect	a × b	-.18	.38	-1.02	.50	-	-
Direct	C	-3.26	1.88	-6.94	.43	-1.74	.083
Total	c + a × b	-3.43	1.90	-7.19	.31	-1.80	.072

Table 8 shows the direct effect of game time on intrinsic motivation (path c), indirect effect of game time through sleep quality (path a × b) and total effect of game time on intrinsic motivation (path c + a × b). The findings revealed that game time does not predict intrinsic motivation ($\beta = -3.26, p>.05$). Further, game time through sleep quality does not predict intrinsic motivation ($\beta = -3.43, p>.05$). The indirect effect was also not statistically significant.

Table 9

Mediation Estimates (Game time= X; Sleep quality = M; Extrinsic motivation = Y)

Effect	Label	Estimate	SE	95% CI		T	P
				LL	UL		
Indirect	a × b	-1.7	3.7	-9.5	.50	-	-
Direct	C	-2.5	2.0	-6.4	1.4	-1.2	2.1
Total	c + a × b	-2.7	2.0	-6.7	1.3	-1.31	.19

Table 9 shows the direct effect of game time on extrinsic motivation (path c), indirect effect of game time through sleep quality (path a × b) and total effect of game time on academic motivation (path c + a × b). The findings revealed that game time does not significantly predict extrinsic motivation ($\beta = -2.5, p > .05$). Further, game time through sleep quality does not predict extrinsic motivation ($\beta = -2.7, p > .05$). The indirect effect was also not statistically significant.

Table 10

Mediation Estimates (Game time = X; Sleep quality = M; Amotivation = Y)

Effect	Label	Estimate	SE	95% CI		T	P
				LL	UL		
Indirect	a × b	-.04	.08	-.21	.11	-	-
Direct	C	-.07	.70	-1.3	1.4	.10	.92
Total	c + a × b	.045	.70	-1.33	1.41	.05	.96

Table 10 shows the direct effect of Game time on Amotivation (path c), indirect effect of game time through sleep quality (path a × b) and total effect of game time on Amotivation (path c + a × b). The findings revealed that Game time does not significantly predict academic motivation. ($\beta = -.07, p > .05$). Further, Game time through sleep quality does not predict academic motivation ($\beta = -.045, p > .96$). The indirect effect was also not statistically significant.

DISCUSSION

The purpose of this study was to investigate the intricate relationship between excessive video game use, sleep quality, and academic motivation among university students. Our study's overarching purpose was to shed light on whether prolonged video game play negatively affects academic motivation, whether sleep quality mediates this link, and whether demographic variables influence these elements differently. The significance of our discoveries, the theoretical foundation, and prospective applications will be explored in greater detail here.

H1: According to hypothesis 1, The excessive use of video games will be negatively associated with sleep quality and academic motivation. Our first hypothesis was that more time spent playing video games would have a detrimental effect on both sleep and academic motivation. Our study did not find a relationship between gaming and academic motivation that was hypothesized, there was no relationship between gaming time and the Academic Motivation Scale, intrinsic motivation Extrinsic motivation and A-motivation as indicated by results of Mediation tables (7-10) and Linear regression table 6, meaning excessive use of video games has no relation with academic motivation and sleep quality.

We also found that excessive use of video games does not cause poor sleep quality, suggesting that there is no favorable association between gaming time and sleep quality. This discovery prompts interesting speculation on gaming's impact on sleep. It could be that since not all gamers exhibit reduced sleep quality and academic motivation because they are excessive gamers and not addicts of video games, that could be the reason for this result

A research was conducted to determine the effect of video games on sleep quality showed that playing video games during day and even before bedtime does not any effect on sleep quality, but instead if a person has history of poor sleep quality then he will have poor sleep quality later on (Hudson., 2018). Another research also showed that amount to time spent on video games is not associated with poor sleep quality (Asbee et al., 2023). Our findings are similar to both of these researches. While excessive gamers and addicted gamers might play video games for same amount of time and are identical behaviorally time they will not have same effect on their lives (Griffiths, 2009), in other words it is the players who are addicted to video games that will have poorer sleep quality and reduced academic motivation as compared to excessive gamers, and hence it can be that excessive gamers in our sample were simply not addicted to video games and that could be the cause of this result

Another research showed results that were contrary to our findings and it showed that poor sleep quality was associated with video games (Neily et al., 20220)
H2: According to hypothesis 2, Sleep quality will affect the relationship between problematic use of video games and academic motivation.. Sleep quality does not have a mediating role in the relationship between video game use and academic motivation, as indicated by non-significant result between the

Sleep Quality Scale (SQS) and the Academic Motivation Scale (AMT).. The mechanisms behind this mediation, such as the effect of sleep on cognitive functioning and mood regulation, should be explored in future studies. Tables 7-10 show that sleep quality does not have a mediating effect between game time and academic motivation.

A research conducted in Indonesia showed that there playing video games does have a relationship with sleep quality and academic motivation (Permana et al ., 2021) Another study also found a link between video gaming and sleep among medical students and that this sleep quality then influences academic performance which is direct predicted of academic motivation..(Babu et al ., 2019), another research found that playing video games for longer periods of time effects sleep quality of university students (Noor et al, 2021) findings of this study are opposite to our findings we did not find a mediating relation of sleep quality with academic motivation and video gaming.

These results could be because players who play video games excessively might not be addicted to them because of which their sleep quality is not affected, Griffiths argues that it is the addiction that takes away something from someone's life such as sleep quality and enthusiastic healthy activity is something that adds something to someone's life and excessive enthusiastic activity and addictive activity are very different things(Griffits,2005a).

H3: According to hypothesis 3, There will be differences based on demographic variables in sleep quality, academic motivation, and excessive use of video games among university students. To test the third hypothesis, we dug further into the data to see if and how demographic factors shaped the associations we found. The impacts of age, gender, and academic semester on sleep quality, academic motivation, and video game use were found to vary. It was found that males play more video games than females These dissimilarities stress the importance of developing specialized interventions and support structures for various student demographics. Gender-specific approaches to encouraging healthy gaming habits and academic motivation, for example, can benefit from knowledge of how gender affects these variables.

Research conducted in Malaysia found no significant differences in gaming time between male and female (Noor et al , 2021). Our research found that there was a significant difference between male and female in terms of gaming time with male

playing more video games as compared to females as can be seen in Table 4.

In conclusion, our research has revealed fascinating relationships between how well you sleep, how much time you spend playing video games, and how much you are motivated to learn in university. Our findings reveal that excessive use of video games does not have any impact on sleep quality and academic motivation.

Additional elements that may affect academic motivation should also be included in future studies, as should the psychological and physiological components of gaming and sleep. The end goal is to create specialized solutions that encourage students to find a happy medium between their gaming and their schoolwork.

Conclusion

In conclusion, our research made a contribution to the expanding body of knowledge regarding the influence of excessive video game use on academic motivation and the mediating role of sleep quality between excessive video game use and academic motivation. Our findings reveal that more males are having an excessive use of video games than females. Excessive use of video games will not have detrimental impact on sleep quality and academic motivation as it might not be the excessive use of video games that will reduce sleep quality and academic motivation but it can be addicted gaming. Future studies should explore whether these findings are consistent among larger sample or whether additional factors such as addiction to video gaming in addition to time spent video gaming

Suggestion:

Future studies should explore whether these findings are consistent among larger sample or whether additional factors such as addiction to video gaming in addition to time spent video gaming .Future research should also focus on whether games played only online are cause of addiction as compared to games that can be played offline. In an increasingly digitized age, it is the hope that educators, counselors, and policymakers will be able to use these findings as a source of information as they work to promote the mental health and academic achievement of university students.

Limitations:

- One of the limitations is that sample was taken from 2 universities in

Wah and Islamabad , sample was smaller it might not represent the entire population of the country

- 2nd limitation is that , the population only had university students , there are many more people who are not in university who play video games
- Addicted gamers were not included in the sample because gaming addiction in universities is extremely rare

DECLARATION

I, **Mr. Muhammad Maratib Ali**, Registration No. **466-FSS/MSCP/F21** student of **MS** in the subject of Psychology, session **2021-2022**, hereby declare that the matter printed in the thesis titled: **IMPACT OF EXCESSIVE USE OF VIDEO GAMES ON ACADEMIC MOTIVATION, MEDIATING ROLE OF SLEEP QUALITY AMONG UNIVERSITY STUDENTS** is my own work and has not been printed, published and submitted as research work, thesis or publication in any form in any University, Research Institution etc in Pakistan or abroad.

RESEARCH COMPLETION CERTIFICATE

Certified that the research work contained in this thesis titled: **IMPACT OF EXCESSIVE USE OF VIDEO GAMES ON ACADEMIC MOTIVATION, MEDIATING ROLE OF SLEEP QUALITY AMONG UNIVERSITY STUDENTS** has been carried out and completed by Mr. Muhammad Maratib Ali, Registration No. **466-FSS/MSCP/F21** under my supervision.

Dedication

This study is dedicated to my Parents and teachers who have been a source of inspiration for me and who gave me strength and provided their support whenever I needed it.

To my family member and friends who shared their words of advice and encouragement in finishing up this study

To my father Dr Arshad Mehmood who's support helped me in this study

To my sister Fatima Arshad who's financial support helped me in this study

To my Supervisor Dr Marzhar Iqbal Bhatti who's continuous input helped me in this study.

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All regards to Holy Prophet Hazrat Muhammad (SAW) who is forever a source of guidance and knowledge for humanity, enabled me to recognize my creator and to know the philosophy of life.

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6. ANNEXURES

Annexure A

Informed Consent

Respected participant, I am a student of MS Clinical Psychology enrolled in International Islamic University Islamabad, I am doing research in video games with the topic “Impact of excessive use of video games on academic motivation; mediating role of sleep quality”. To assess the constructs a few questionnaire are required to be completed. It is ensured that the data provided will be kept confidential and will only be used for research purposes and the respondent will be kept confidential and will not be disclosed in any publication. There is not time limit to the completion of the questionnaire and the respondent may quit at any time. Your cooperation will be greatly appreciated in providing valuable information. Thank you

Do you want to participate in the research :Yes / No

Annexure B

DEMOGRAPHIC SHEET

NAME:

AGE:

GENDER :

CLASS:

Annexure C
Sleep Quality Scale (SQS)
Examples

Rarely : None or 1-3 times a month

Sometimes : 1-2 times a week

Often : 3-5 times a week

Almost always : 6-7 times a week

Question	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Almost always
I have difficulty falling asleep				
I fall into a deep sleep				
I wake up while sleeping				
I have difficulty getting back to sleep once I wake up				
I wake up easily because of noise				
I toss and turn				
I never go back to sleep after awaking during sleep				
I feel refreshed after sleep				
I feel unlikely to sleep after sleep				
Poor sleep gives me headaches				
Poor sleep makes me irritated				
I would like to sleep more after waking up				
My sleep hours are enough				
Poor sleep makes me loose my apetite				
Poor sleep makes hard for me to think				
I feel vigorous after sleep				
I am satisfied with my sleep				
Poor sleep makes me forget things more easily				
Poor sleep make it hard to concentrate at work				
Sleepiness interferes with my daily life				
Poor sleep makes me loose desire in all things				
I have difficulty getting out of bed				
Poor sleep makes me easily tired at work				
I have a clear head after sleep				
Poor sleep make my life painful				

Annexure D
Additional Screening Information

Gaming Addiction Scale (GAS)

On average how many hours a day do you play video games	Less than 4 hours		More than 4 hours		
Question	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Very often
Did you think about playing a game all day?					
Did you spend increasing amount of time on games?					
Did you play games to forget about real life					
Have others unsuccessfully tried to reduce your time in games?					
Have you felt bad when you were unable to play?					

Did you have fights with other (eg family friends) over time spent on games?					
Have you neglected other important activities(e.g school) to play games?					

Annexure E
Academic Motivation Scale(AMS)
Why do you go to University?

Does not correspond at all	Corresponds a little	Corresponds moderately	Corresponds a lot	Corresponds exactly		
1	2	3	4	5	6	7

Question	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Because with only a high-school degree I would not find a high-paying job later on							
Because I experience pleasure and satisfaction while learning new things.							
Because I think that a college education will help me better prepare for the career I have chosen							
For the intense feelings I experience when I am communicating my own ideas to others.							
Honestly, I don't know; I really feel that I am wasting my time in school.							
For the pleasure I experience while surpassing myself in my studies							
To prove to myself that I am capable of completing my college degree.							
In order to obtain a more prestigious job later on							
For the pleasure I experience when I discover new things never seen before.							
Because eventually it will enable me to enter the job market in a field that I like.							
For the pleasure that I experience when I read interesting authors.							
I once had good reasons for going to college; however, now I wonder whether I should continue							
For the pleasure that I experience while I am surpassing myself in one of my personal accomplishments.							
Because of the fact that when I succeed in college I feel important.							
Because I want to have "the good life" later on.							
For the pleasure that I experience in broadening my knowledge about subjects which appeal to me.							
Because this will help me make a better choice regarding my career orientation.							

For the pleasure that I experience when I feel completely absorbed by what certain authors have written.							
I can't see why I go to college and frankly, I couldn't care less							
For the satisfaction I feel when I am in the process of accomplishing difficult academic activities.							
To show myself that I am an intelligent person							
In order to have a better salary later on.							
Because my studies allow me to continue to learn about many things that interest me.							
Because I believe that a few additional years of education will improve my competence as a worker							
For the "high" feeling that I experience while reading about various interesting subjects.							
I don't know; I can't understand what I am doing in school.							
Because college allows me to experience a personal satisfaction in my quest for excellence in my studies							
Because I want to show myself that I can succeed in my studies							

